

Building trust through values

Measurement of Community Health Indicators
(MoCHI) project report

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Executive Summary

From January through December 2025, IOI conducted the MoCHI project to ask: How applicable and useful are evaluation frameworks and metrics in incentivizing investment in and adoption of open infrastructure for research? Using interviews, co-design workshops, and participatory validation with infrastructure providers, funders, and adopters, the project tested the hypothesis that identifying shared values and measuring adherence to them could help strengthen ecosystem resilience. Our central finding was more nuanced: stakeholders operate in constant tension between aspirational values (open principles, community service, academy-owned outputs) and practical constraints (budgets, procurement processes, institutional requirements). Successful infrastructure evaluation requires tools that help stakeholders navigate these tensions.

Through interviews and workshops, we identified 11 themes that stakeholders mentioned as key for their evaluation process:

- **Data Ownership, Portability, and Control:** the only theme rated "Very Important" by all stakeholder groups. Stakeholders care deeply about maintaining control over what they put into systems.
- **Affordability:** About value relative to cost, not simply low price. Contextual: a threshold requirement for some; a value-for-investment calculus for others.
- **Technical Requirements:** Features, integrations, and compatibility with existing skills. Should include ease of adoption, not just a feature checklist.
- **Transparent Governance:** Clear understanding of who makes decisions and how.
- **Fiscal Security:** Adequate, sustainable funding to cover costs and build reserves. Critical but hardest to assess; negative indicators are easier to spot than positive proof.
- **Support and Technical Training:** Broader than official documentation — includes peer support, third-party resources, vendor ecosystems, and self-service capacity.
- **Policy and Regulatory Compliance:** Binary threshold: non-negotiable when it applies; irrelevant when it doesn't.
- **Sense of Community and Belonging:** Effective community input mechanisms and inclusive culture. Distinction between feeling heard and having actual decision-making power.
- **Longevity and Embeddedness:** Well-established, actively used, known in the field. Can signal stability or technical debt; past resilience does not guarantee future resilience.

- **Usage and Adoption:** Relevant to and adopted by peer organizations. Innovation vs. stability tension: high adoption signals quality but can preclude transformational infrastructure.
- **Values Alignment and Community Orientation:** Captures whether infrastructure is mission-driven vs. profit-driven and genuinely puts community first.

In addition, the concept of **resilience (financial, technical, political, and organizational)** emerged repeatedly across workshops and themes as a critical forward-looking dimension not fully captured by any single theme.

Values shape behaviour, but don't determine it. Stakeholders make pragmatic decisions constrained by cost, capacity, institutional policies, and switching costs, often accepting trade-offs that don't fully reflect their stated ideals. The relative importance of each theme is strongly related to context, including the needs of a particular stakeholder and their community and the timing of an evaluation exercise.

The way our participants talked about open infrastructure often, ultimately, came down to **trust**: that scholarly outputs and research data will remain accessible, that infrastructure will serve community needs over pursuit of profit, that decisions will be made transparently, and that participants can exit if things change. The evaluation themes we identified are some of the criteria that different stakeholders called on in developing and articulating that trust.

Introduction

The past decade has seen a proliferation of frameworks and tools designed to help organizations evaluate the health, sustainability, and values-alignment of open infrastructure. Some of these frameworks speak to specific communities or contexts, such as [CHAOSS](#) (Community Health Analytics in Open Source Software), a Linux Foundation project that developed metrics and models focused on the technical health of open source software communities. [HuMetricsHSS](#) took a values-first approach to assessment designed for humanities and social science scholars and their institutions. [POSI](#) (Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructure) offered a set of governance, sustainability, and insurance principles tailored to scholarly infrastructure organizations.

From January through December 2025, Invest in Open Infrastructure (IOI) conducted the Measurement of Community Health Indicators (MoCHI) project, supported by the Digital Infrastructure Insights Fund. This research used the concept of “community health” from the CHAOSS project as a lens to explore a fundamental question about decision-making in the open infrastructure ecosystem: **How applicable and useful are evaluation frameworks and metrics in incentivizing investment in and adoption of open infrastructure for research?**

Through interviews, co-design workshops, and participatory validation with infrastructure providers, funders, and adopters, we identified 11 key evaluation themes that stakeholders consistently reference when making infrastructure decisions. Our findings reveal that values matter deeply and exist in constant tension with practical constraints, and that successful infrastructure evaluation requires tools that help stakeholders navigate these tensions rather than simply checking boxes. While seeking to answer questions about evaluation frameworks, we discovered an underlying layer of values and trade-offs that stakeholders and community members use across contexts, ultimately building on **trust** rather than metrics that measure a community’s health.

Initial research questions

The open research infrastructure landscape is remarkably complex, with hundreds of tools available across research workflows. Funders need to make strategic investments, adopters need to choose platforms that will serve their communities, and infrastructure providers need to demonstrate their value and sustainability. Our central research question asked: **How applicable and useful are evaluation frameworks and metrics in incentivizing investment in and adoption of open infrastructure for research?**

This question rested on a hypothesis: if there are identifiable common values among our focus populations (providers, funders, and adopters), and if stronger adherence to those values increases the worth of and/or correlates to more resilience and longevity for particular tools and services, then measuring and demonstrating values alignment may incentivize these focus populations to make collective investments that strengthen ecosystem resilience.

As we framed it at the project's start: "Open" is a set of values. Values shape behaviour.

We wanted to understand:

- Do existing community health frameworks inform infrastructure decisions?
- What factors do stakeholders actually evaluate when choosing, funding, or building infrastructure?
- Can we identify shared language and common priorities across different stakeholder groups?
- How can tools like [Infra Finder](#), which provides information about key characteristics of open infrastructures, use these shared values to better support decision-makers?

Project outline

Three-phase participatory research approach

Phase 1: Discovery through desk research and interviews (January-May 2025)

We studied three major frameworks that are used to assess community health for research infrastructure, which had surfaced in other research projects at IOI. We compared the key metrics across these three frameworks for commonalities and shared themes.

- [CHAOSS](#) (Community Health Analytics in Open Source Software), developed by the Linux Foundation, provides a set of metrics and models designed to measure the health and sustainability of open source software communities, focusing on areas like community activity, contributor diversity, organizational participation, and project responsiveness.
- [FOREST](#), created by Sarah Lippincott and Katherine Skinner for the Educopia Institute, offers a values-driven assessment framework specifically designed for

scholarly communication infrastructures, addressing financial and organizational resilience, openness and interoperability, representative governance, equity and accessibility, sharing of knowledge, and transparency.

- [POSI](#) (Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructure), developed collaboratively by multiple scholarly infrastructure organizations in 2015 and maintained as a community resource, articulates a set of principles for the governance, sustainability, and operation of scholarly infrastructure, emphasizing aspects like stakeholder governance, non-discriminatory membership, transparent operations, community-driven change, and the ability to survive organizational transitions.

We then conducted in-depth interviews with a cross-section of open infrastructure stakeholders:

- Open Infrastructure Providers (organizations that build and maintain research infrastructure),
- Funders and Buyers (organizations that invest in or purchase infrastructure for their institutions),
- Adopters and End Users (organizations and individuals who use infrastructure directly).

Each interview had two parts:

1. Understanding awareness and familiarity with existing community health frameworks (CHAOSS, FOREST, POSI).
2. Exploring how participants made decisions about infrastructure in practice.

Phase 2: Analysis and theme identification (May-August 2025)

From interview analysis, we identified 11 recurring evaluation themes that stakeholders referenced when making infrastructure decisions. These themes cut across stakeholder types and represented both aspirational values (what people want to prioritize) and practical constraints (what they must consider).

We published our initial findings in May 2025 as part of IOI's State of Open Infrastructure report in a chapter titled "[Trust, transparency, and technology: Do community health frameworks shape open infrastructure decisions?](#)" These findings were also discussed in a CHAOSScast podcast ([Episode 112](#)), and in a blog post titled "[Building bridges: How trust and community health frameworks can strengthen open infrastructure decision-making](#)".

Phase 3: Co-design workshops and validation (September-December 2025)

We brought stakeholders back together in three role-specific workshops (providers, buyers/funders, and adopters/users) to validate and refine our findings: Each workshop included:

1. **Pre-workshop activity:** Participants sorted the 11 themes into categories (Important, Very Important, Not So Important) based on their organization's priorities.
2. **Collaborative discussion:** Using Mural boards, participants reviewed aggregated results, discussed similarities and differences, and provided feedback on theme definitions and terminology.
3. **Synthesis and refinement:** We captured detailed notes on what resonated, what needed clarification, and what was missing.

The goal of these workshops was to ensure the framework genuinely reflected stakeholder perspectives rather than imposing academic categories. We used feedback and discussion from these workshops to further refine the themes.

Integration with Infra Finder

Throughout the project, we examined how the themes and considerations revealed from this project mapped to data available in [Infra Finder](#), IOI's discovery tool for open research infrastructure. We found that while some elements could benefit from additional data gathering and small language adjustments, overall, data relevant to each theme was represented in Infra Finder's existing dataset. This validation led to adjustments in our discovery tool, including moving certain information to closely align with related fields and editing the language in our questions and descriptions.

Findings

Community health frameworks: Limited awareness, specific utility

Most interview participants had not heard of CHAOSS, FOREST, or POSI before our conversations. This doesn't mean the frameworks aren't useful; rather, their utility is context-specific rather than universal.

The frameworks excel in certain niches:

- **CHAOS** is valuable for infrastructure providers doing a self-assessment of their community health and open source project vitality.
- **FOREST** provides guidance specifically for scholarly communication infrastructure around financial sustainability, governance, equity, and transparency.
- **POSI** offers aspirational principles for infrastructure governance and sustainability.

Workshop feedback confirmed that these frameworks are good internal assessment tools but were of limited utility as decision-making tools for funders or adopters.

The tension between aspiration and practicality

Our most significant finding challenged our initial assumptions. We began thinking that evaluation frameworks were primarily aspirational statements of values that infrastructure should strive toward. What we discovered was more nuanced: stakeholders operate in constant tension between aspirational values and practical constraints. This factor was key to assessing the limited utility of the three community health frameworks under discussion.

As one workshop participant explained, their ideal values don't always align with the decisions they actually make due to institutional requirements and resource limitations. Another noted a specific tension in their work where they rely heavily on an expensive, non-ideal commercial tool despite knowing it doesn't align well with their values, because the combination of usage patterns, cost structure, and switching costs keeps them locked in. Participants described this as a "seesaw," where changing context means a constant shift in which end of the seesaw matters more.

Figure 1: The aspiration vs. practicality see-saw.

Stakeholders operate in constant tension between aspirational values and practical constraints.

Context is crucial

A consistent finding across all workshops: the importance of any evaluation criterion depends entirely on context. The same person evaluates infrastructure differently depending on which hat they're wearing. Evaluation for adoption differs from evaluation for funding, which differs from evaluation for partnership. A funding focus means evaluating potential impact and sustainability; someone going through an adoption process might focus on evaluating fit for their community's needs; and those who are focused on making and maintaining tools may evaluate their own capacity and values alignment.

Data sovereignty is a universal priority

Data Ownership, Portability, and Control was the only theme to receive "Very Important" ratings from all participants across all workshops. One adopter explained that their community and stakeholders feel more strongly about what they put into systems than about the systems themselves, and it is the data and content that truly matter. An infrastructure provider noted that their multi-decade track record has built strong trust with their community, specifically because they chose to prioritize data sovereignty and user control.

This finding suggests data sovereignty transcends role, geography, and organizational context as a foundational requirement for trust in open infrastructure. It reflects deep concerns about:

- Vendor lock-in and the ability to exit if infrastructure direction changes,
- Commercial capture of scholarly outputs and research data,
- Researcher and institutional control over their own work,
- Transparency about how collected data is used.

Values alignment and community orientation

In our initial research, we labelled one theme "Loyalty and Benevolence," intending to capture concepts around trust, reputation, and community-first decision-making. However, this terminology generated significant confusion and debate across all three workshops. Participants consistently questioned what "loyalty" meant and to whom it was directed, and suggested the framing didn't accurately capture what they valued.

Through workshop discussions, we clarified that what stakeholders actually care about is:

- **Values alignment:** Does the infrastructure's mission align with ours?
- **Community-first orientation:** Are decisions driven more by community needs or profit maximization?
- **Trustworthiness:** Has the infrastructure earned trust through consistent action?
- **Social contract:** Will the infrastructure maintain its commitment to users even when that conflicts with potential profit?

Based on this feedback, we renamed this theme "Values Alignment and Community Orientation" to better reflect what stakeholders are actually evaluating. The revised framing emphasizes whether infrastructure operates on mission-driven versus purely profit-driven incentives, and whether the community's interests genuinely guide decision-making.

Affordability is about value

Participants in all three workshops discussed affordability as complex and contextual, not simply about low cost. While some described affordability as a threshold requirement (if they can't fund implementation, the infrastructure is immediately off the table), others reframed affordability as being about value received relative to cost, emphasizing that it's not just a budget proportion issue but rather whether they're getting sufficient benefit for the investment.

Adopters noted that affordability considerations extend beyond immediate costs to include long-term sustainability of creating, maintaining, and stewarding infrastructure. Infrastructure providers discussed the challenge of articulating value and quantifying return on investment for potential members or funders, noting that it's particularly difficult to put a price tag on the benefits of free and open source software.

Fiscal security is critical but hard to assess

All three workshops identified fiscal security as both important and difficult to evaluate, particularly from outside an organization. Infrastructure providers described challenges in

getting members to fund infrastructure they receive for free, and the difficulty of demonstrating sustainable business models. Funders acknowledged fiscal security as a very important criterion but noted it's extremely difficult to assess or demand specific markers beyond pricing information and fiscal history.

One adopter noted an important insight: while it may be hard to know whether a project is fiscally secure, it's often easy to identify when it isn't. This suggests negative indicators (signs of fiscal insecurity) may be more detectable than positive proof of sustainability. Put simply: red flags are easier to spot than green lights.

Usage and adoption: Innovation vs. stability trade-off

This theme revealed a fundamental tension that split participants across all workshops.

Having peer organizations use the same platform makes building integrations and enhancements easier. Institutions might prefer established tools specifically because of their proven track record, and experience with existing implementations can help streamline procurement processes and make infrastructure easier for new users to adopt.

However, supporting innovative infrastructure sometimes means accepting that it doesn't have widespread adoption. Being overly focused on existing, highly-adopted infrastructure could preclude support for transformational or boundary-pushing infrastructure.

This theme represents a trade-off between innovation and stability that different stakeholders navigate differently based on their risk tolerance and goals, and is one of the key tensions that must be addressed when evaluating open infrastructure.

Transparent governance is not necessarily participatory governance

Participants identified governance and transparent decision-making as key factors in building trust in an infrastructure. However, being able to see governance structures (transparency) is different from being able to participate in them (participatory governance). The right level of governance engagement depends on the relationship and the stakes involved. Some stakeholders just need to understand how decisions are made. Others need actual decision-making power and influence as a condition of their support or adoption. Participants also noted that participating in the governance or advisory group for an infrastructure is one measure of developing a sense of community and belonging, and a strong way to foster trust. This participation is difficult to assess from outside of an organization, however, and relies on clear communication.

Support extends beyond official documentation

Multiple workshops noted that "Support and Technical Training" is broader than just what the infrastructure provider offers. Providers discussed the tension between institutions adopting infrastructure themselves and those that need vendor support, and how their community support ecosystems function beyond official channels. Adopters noted that they must evaluate whether sufficient community support exists, whether there is sufficient documentation from other users, and whether peer-to-peer assistance is available. One noted that alternative ways of meeting support needs beyond official infrastructure team generosity can be just as valuable.

Support includes peer-to-peer community support, third-party documentation, blog posts from users, vendor ecosystems, and self-service capacity — not just official technical training from the provider. Infrastructure that enables community-driven support may be more sustainable than infrastructure that tries to provide all support internally.

The policy and regulatory compliance theme is binary when it applies

All three workshops acknowledged this theme has a unique characteristic: when it matters, it's non-negotiable; when it doesn't matter, it's irrelevant.

Multiple funders rated policy compliance as a top priority, noting that policy compliance operates at a different level than other criteria because if an infrastructure is not in compliance, it can't receive funding. On the other hand, providers and adopters who don't operate in heavily regulated spaces (such as those that don't handle medical data) rated it as unimportant because it simply does not apply to them.

Adopters noted an interesting nuance: officially, the theme might be very important, but in practice, it may matter less because exceptions can be made or policies can change within institutions.

Longevity can signal stability or technical debt

Multiple workshops showed that longevity is not universally positive, as the longer a software product is around, the more opportunity it has to accrue technical debt.

Providers had contrasting perspectives. One emphasized that 27 years of longevity matters significantly because it demonstrates the ability to survive in a volatile landscape where many infrastructures don't have staying power, and this longevity has built strong

community trust. However, another noted that longevity didn't serve their infrastructure well during a major version change that left some users behind.

Funders questioned whether longevity might indicate flexibility or inflexibility, noting that resilience demonstrated in the last 10-15 years might not indicate resilience to today's disruptions. This discussion revealed an underlying consideration that was evident across multiple themes: resilience.

Resilience emerges as a critical consideration for funders

Workshop discussions, particularly among funders, repeatedly highlighted "resilience" as an important concept that was not well captured in our 11 themes. Funders identified multiple dimensions of resilience that matter for infrastructure evaluation:

- **Financial resilience:** Can the infrastructure weather funding fluctuations and maintain operations through financial uncertainty?
- **Technical resilience:** Can it adapt to new technologies and handle increased load? One funder noted that dramatic traffic increases from AI scraping and other harvesting tools present a key current issue that infrastructures must be able to handle.
- **Political resilience:** Can it operate across different political regimes and remain insulated from political interference? The ability to keep operating and providing services despite political disruption was noted as increasingly important amid active funding instability across multiple jurisdictions during this project's duration.
- **Organizational resilience:** Is the infrastructure distributed rather than dependent on a single person or organization? Does it have sufficient people with the right skills and business acumen to maintain operations if key individuals leave?

Resilience is forward-looking (can we adapt to future disruptions?) while longevity is backward-looking (have we survived past challenges?).

An infrastructure might have impressive longevity but lack resilience to entirely new types of challenges.

The 11 themes

We distilled the findings from our background research and interviews into 11 themes that stakeholders consistently referenced when evaluating open infrastructure. Based on participants' feedback about the specific utility of checklists and their desire for a different kind of framework, we deliberately avoided creating a checklist-style tool. Instead, we framed these as themes that represent the values and practical considerations that come into tension during decision-making. These themes were introduced to participants after the interviews but before the group workshops, and refined after feedback during the workshops.

The 11 themes are listed below and further described in Table 1.

Data Ownership, Portability, and Control
Affordability
Technical Requirements
Transparent Governance
Fiscal Security
Support and Technical Training
Policy and Regulatory Compliance
Sense of Community and Belonging
Longevity and Embeddedness
Usage and Adoption
Values Alignment and Community Orientation

Theme	Explanation	Details from Participants
Data Ownership, Portability, and Control	Users retain ownership of their content and data; clear exit strategies exist; transparent data use policies	Universal priority across ALL groups. Only theme with a unanimous "Very Important" rating. Stakeholders care intensely about what they put into systems and maintaining control over their data and content.
Affordability	Total cost of ownership is within budget	Complex, not simple cost. About value relative to cost, resources, and alternatives. Context-dependent: threshold requirement for some; balanced against other factors for others. Includes long-term sustainability costs.
Technical Requirements	Features, integrations, compatibility with needs and in-house skills	Context-dependent. Importance varies by role and existing technical capacity. Should include ease of adoption, not just a feature checklist.
Transparent Governance	Clear understanding of who makes decisions and how	Hard to assess from the outside. Transparency ≠ participation. Some stakeholders just need to understand; others need decision-making power as a condition of support.
Fiscal Security	Adequate funding to cover costs and establish reserves; sustainable revenue	Critical but hardest to assess. Information is often opaque. Negative indicators (fiscal insecurity) are easier to spot than positive proof.
Support and Technical Training	Support services available from provider or third parties	Broader than official documentation. Includes peer support, blog posts, vendor ecosystem, and self-service capacity. Community-driven support may matter more than official training.

Policy and Regulatory Compliance	Meets institutional requirements for security, accessibility, legal form	Binary threshold. When it applies, it's non-negotiable and eliminates non-compliant options. When it doesn't apply to your context, it's irrelevant.
Sense of Community and Belonging	Effective community input mechanisms; inclusive, welcoming community	Overlaps with governance. Distinction between feeling heard and actual decision-making power. Community responsiveness is hard to verify from the outside.
Longevity and Embeddedness	Well-established; in active use over time; known in research community	Can signal stability or technical debt. Past resilience does not indicate future resilience. Name recognition matters, but can also indicate inflexibility.
Usage and Adoption	Relevant to and adopted by similar users; identifiable peers	Innovation vs. stability tension. High adoption signals quality and eases integration, but can preclude transformational infrastructure. Ease of adoption matters, not just numbers.
Values Alignment and Community Orientation	Infrastructure mission aligns with stakeholder values; decisions driven by community needs rather than profit; trustworthy track record	Originally called "Loyalty and Benevolence" but renamed based on workshop feedback. Captures the distinction between mission-driven vs. profit-driven incentives. Social contract and community-first orientation matter.

Table 1: 11 themes for evaluating open infrastructure, as identified in interviews, workshops, and feedback from three groups of stakeholders (open infrastructure providers, adopters, and funders).

Key takeaways

Values matter, and so do constraints. "Open" is indeed a set of values, and while values can shape behaviour, they don't necessarily determine behaviour. Stakeholders make pragmatic decisions that balance aspirational values with real-world constraints such as cost, capacity, institutional policies, network effects, and switching costs.

One size doesn't fit all, and that is acceptable. The importance of any evaluation criterion is inherently contextual. A framework or tool that tries to be universal risks being useless to everyone.

Data sovereignty is non-negotiable. Data Ownership, Portability, and Control was the only theme that received universal strong agreement across all stakeholder groups. This reflects deep concern about vendor lock-in, commercial capture of scholarly outputs, researcher control over their own work, and transparency about data use.

Values alignment and community orientation need clear framing. What stakeholders care about when evaluating infrastructure is whether the organization's values align with theirs and whether the infrastructure truly puts community interests first. This includes mission alignment, decision-making driven by community needs rather than profit extraction, trust earned through consistent action, and commitment to users maintained even when it conflicts with profit maximization.

Resilience is an underlying consideration across many themes. Workshop discussions repeatedly identified resilience as critical but not well-captured in our existing themes. Resilience encompasses multiple dimensions: financial (weathering funding fluctuations), technical (adapting to new technologies and handling increased loads), political (operating across different political regimes), and organizational/community (distributed capacity rather than single points of failure). Resilience is forward-looking while longevity is backward-looking.

Assessment requires multiple modes of information. Different themes require different types of information and verification: factual verification (technical features, licensing, location), transparency documents (financial statements, governance policies, security practices), reputation signals (community feedback, peer recommendations, track record), and demonstrated behaviour (how they handled past challenges, transitions, or conflicts). Some of the most important themes are also the hardest to assess from outside an organization.

Negative indicators may be more detectable than positive proof. Red flags are often easier to spot than green lights. Signs of fiscal insecurity, governance dysfunction, or community dissatisfaction may be more visible than positive proof of health.

Revealed preferences matter as much as stated values. Multiple workshops acknowledged a gap between what people want to value and what they actually prioritize in practice. This pragmatic reality doesn't make values meaningless; it makes understanding constraints essential.

Conclusion

We started this project with a very different idea of “community health” in open infrastructure than we had when the project ended. We found that the tools and frameworks available help infrastructure communities assess and develop their communities in healthy ways; meanwhile, another underlying set of considerations emerged through discussions of evaluations of community health. The MoCHI project explored those underlying values that matter in open infrastructure decision-making and revealed that these values exist in constant, productive tension with practical realities.

We found remarkable agreement on core priorities, such as data sovereignty, alongside significant diversity in how stakeholders navigate trade-offs. We discovered that existing community health frameworks serve important but specific purposes, and that the ecosystem needs complementary tools for different use cases.

We learned that the path forward isn't about making “one framework to rule them all”, but about developing clearer shared language, making information more accessible, helping stakeholders navigate trade-offs, and building tools that meet different stakeholders where they are

The way our participants talked about open infrastructure often, ultimately, came down to **trust**: that our scholarly outputs and research data will remain accessible, that infrastructure will serve community needs over profit extraction, that decisions will be made transparently, and that we can exit if things change. The evaluation themes we identified are some of the criteria that different stakeholders called on in developing and articulating that trust.

By understanding how different stakeholders evaluate infrastructure, what information they need, and how they navigate competing priorities, we can build a more resilient, more trustworthy, more sustainable open infrastructure ecosystem.

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Resources and Outputs

Blog Posts

- Collister, L., Wu, C., Lippincott, S., & Skinner, K. (2026, March 13.) "Building trust through values: Measurement of Community Health Indicators (MoCHI) project report." Invest in Open Infrastructure.
<https://investinopen.org/blog/building-trust-through-values/>
- Skinner, K., Wu, C., Lippincott, S., & Collister, L. (2025, October 3.) What do institutions need to know before choosing open infrastructure? Invest in Open Infrastructure.
<https://investinopen.org/blog/what-do-institutions-need-to-know-before-choosing-open-infrastructure/>
- Tsang, E. (2025, June 19.) Building bridges: How trust and community health frameworks can strengthen open infrastructure decision-making. Invest in Open Infrastructure.
<https://investinopen.org/blog/building-bridges-how-trust-and-community-health-frameworks-can-strengthen-open-infrastructure-decision-making/>
- Skinner, K., & Tsang, E. (2024, November 25). Announcing our new research on community health assessments for open infrastructure. Invest in Open Infrastructure.
<https://investinopen.org/blog/announcing-our-new-research-on-community-health-assessments-for-open-infrastructure/>

Reports

- Collister, L., Wu, C., Lippincott, S., & Skinner, K. (2026, March 13.) "Building trust through values: Measurement of Community Health Indicators (MoCHI) project report." Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18929158>
- "Trust, transparency, and technology: Do community health frameworks share open infrastructure decisions?" In 2025 State of Open Infrastructure Report.
<https://investinopen.org/state-of-open-infrastructure-2025/sooi-signals-from-the-field-2025/#trust-transparency-and-technology-do-community-health-frameworks-share-open-infrastructure-decisions>

Podcasts

- CHAOSScast, 12 June 2025. "[Community health metrics and open infrastructure decision making — with Chrys Wu, Invest in Open Infrastructure.](#)"

Grant Proposal

- Skinner, K., Collister, L., & Wu, C. (2025). Grant Proposal: Incentivizing Investment in and Adoption of Open Infrastructure for Research through Community Health Assessments. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15052274>

Contributor roles

We use the Contributor Roles Taxonomy (CRediT) to specify collaborators' contributions: <https://credit.niso.org/>.

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